

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENTAL PROBLEMS IN CHILDREN IN THE MODERN AGE

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Abstract

In the modern age, developmental problems in children have taken on a complex structure with various socio-cultural, digital and psychological effects. The following problems stand out among these:

1. Digital addiction and screen time: The widespread use of technology can lead to increased screen addiction in children, negatively affecting the development of social skills. Excessive screen time, especially at young ages, can lead to physical and mental health problems such as attention deficit, sleep problems and obesity.

2. Social isolation: Socializing in the digital world can replace face-to-face communication. This can prevent children from developing social skills, empathy and understanding group dynamics.

3. Academic pressures and perfectionism: In the modern age, pressure for education and careers is increasing. This can cause emotional problems such as stress, anxiety and depression in children.

4. Emotional and psychological problems: Social media and online platforms can create an ideal "perfect life" perception in children, causing self-confidence problems and body image disorders. Bullying, social pressures and constant comparisons can negatively affect children's psychological health.

5. Changes in family dynamics: Changes in family structure (divorce, single-parent families, dual-career parents) and parents' busy work schedules can affect children's emotional development. Children who do not receive enough attention and support may experience delays in their emotional development.

6. Hyperactivity and attention deficit disorder (ADHD): In the modern age, the diagnosis of such disorders has become more common. Hyperactivity, concentration problems and impulsive behaviors in children can make the educational process and social relationships difficult.

In order to overcome these developmental problems, families, educators and social organizations should take responsibility for providing more support to children.

Keywords: child, family, development, developmental problems.

Main content

It is emphasized that almost all of the books written on education are a social entity. If this is the case, then it is important to see the current society and the social life that the society is involved in, its separation, especially the question "What comes to the conversations in the world?" in recent years?" What do they experience? You need to point out: We can see that there are three main areas of change that children have encountered and been affected by in recent years... the first of which is "consumption in life". Prices in market markets increase competition by exploiting the individual's desires for consumption alone, taking into account other (social - emotional) desires of the individual. On weekends or in the evenings, after work or school, people go to indoor places again. With the change in technology, everything is conditioned to be consumed, this is constantly pumped through mass media, owning the same object more than once even though it is not necessary, and being surrounded by technological tools and equipment as a result of consumption. These are the consequences of losses.

In order for children to survive in the globalizing economy, school forces them to work harder. Extended family ties can reduce the negativities in this regard, but these ties also weaken due to the increase in the development levels of the countries. In addition to this negative trend, there is the problem of sacrificing the "public" for the "private" and this situation is spreading to all countries, like the world bank policy. Let's say we all live in one neighborhood. There are many houses

and buildings... There are grocery stores, butchers, greengrocers... However, there should also be green areas, parks and gardens in this neighborhood. Who has the right to have all these things? In general, it is the right of citizens living in a society.

Accordingly, the second area of change, that is, the "decrease in children's street relationships", has emerged. In the past, children could spend their days and play on the streets, but this is no longer possible, especially in big cities. Unfortunately, there are no empty lots where they can play freely, no parks where they can dream and do mischief, and no neighborhoods where they can play with mud, jump rope and play ball comfortably. Instead, there are spaces surrounded by concrete. Although people live in private sites and are in a globalized communication network, neighborly relations are decreasing. Due to increased mobility, both adults and children come together with more people, but real communication is difficult and face-to-face and eye contact are avoided. This situation does not have positive results in terms of our social emotional life.

The third area of change is "general environmental problems". While children are aware of general problems, they are also moving away from their natural areas. As a result of all these changes in life, we are faced with a youth that is deprived of nature and spontaneity, feels better in closed spaces, is withdrawn and cannot even understand that he is sick. In order to reduce the impact of this negative trend all over the world, the first thing that needs to be done is to ensure people's right to education.

These areas of change in our lives make it very difficult for parents to cope with their children. Especially families living in big cities - many of which are working mothers and fathers with one child - cannot cope with their children and cannot adjust the balance of freedom and boundaries. However, if "yes" and "no" are desired, they are arranged so well that children both feel freedom and perceive limits. The likelihood of people of all ages, and especially children, being spiritually healthy increases as their energies are directed to areas of interest that can be spent positively and they are provided with environments and opportunities where they can express themselves. This development enables them to be successful in social life, to have self-confidence and to develop a positive sense of self. Without this groundwork, the individual cannot be expected to have intrinsic motivation, which has a very important place in studying and academic success. Parents must first learn and accept this fact. In addition, academic success does not only consist of success in science and mathematics; academic success cannot be evaluated by considering only one aspect of our cognitive structure. By developing our different talent areas, success can be achieved in those areas; for example; in sports, health issues, social issues, foreign language learning, communication skills... However, unfortunately, the last things I have mentioned do not count as success... As you know, our children's social issues lessons or physical education and visual arts lessons are sometimes among the missing lessons or During those class hours, lessons on mathematics, science and technology subjects that are perceived to be important are given. In other words, these courses are not given the importance they should be.

If this understanding were correct, the result of all this hard work and going to private teaching institutions would be as follows; Azerbaijani children would get higher scores than children of other countries in all science and mathematics-based surveys... However, the results of the research show that we are almost at the bottom. Our main problem is that we do not have the necessary consistency and continuity in the systems we have introduced, especially in the national education systems.

Play is an environment where children reflect on everything they can and cannot cope with, that is, their lives. Play is the child's job. What we need to do is to prepare the appropriate time and environment for the game. To guide by preparing an environment full of rich stimulants, to prepare the environment and then to stand back... It discovers the rest anyway... The period of "0 - 8 years", which we call early childhood, is already a period based on "discovery" and "curiosity"... Parents interrupt their children's games, They think that things will be solved by destroying his social interests and forcing him to go to the computer or test books. However, learning cannot take place unless the child is ready and receives appropriate education and training. If parents do not know how to care for and support their children, they cannot raise their children properly. Or, after the working mother comes home in the evening, she worries about not being able to spare enough time for her child and directs all her attention, money and

everything to the child and if she does whatever she wants, that child will of course be spoiled.

Published research or books about the game tell us; In the early period, the child needs to spend most of the day playing freely. Moreover, their hands will be involved; in mud, in bugs, in the garden, in repairs, in construction work. Because children learn best while playing. When you go to other countries, they allow children to take free walks in natural environments untouched by human hands, for one hour in the morning and in the evening. Moreover, children do not talk to those around them. He just looks, studies nature. This ability to make observations is primarily required for cognitive development. Let him observe there, look around, see and examine the flower and insect. Here, the teacher's duty begins when the child comes from a nature trip.

Let's say you made such a trip, you sit down together and ask: "What did you see, what did you hear?" One of the children says, "I heard the sound of a jet plane," the other says, "I didn't hear it," one says, "A bird sang, I heard the sound of a sparrow," the other says, "I saw a turtle, what did you see?" "I heard the sound of a car." Then, if we consider that each of them transfers the information they perceive to their friends, we see how both concept learning and expressive language development can be supported. Moreover, such activities provide children with the opportunity to express themselves and gain the ability to listen to others. In this process, children realize that we all perceive differently and that there are many different objects or entities around us. Noticing the differences is the first stage we must overcome in the cognitive development process. If a person does not notice something, he will not be curious about it or need to be informed. For example; Let's say you are an uneasy person, but you are not aware of it and you are upsetting people. In order to correct your mistakes and compensate for your shortcomings, you must first be aware of yourself so that you can heal yourself and take precautions. In order for children to develop their first skills in mathematics, they need to be aware of their surroundings, be able to make observations and record their observations. Did you know that illiterate children can do this? You give him a piece of paper and say: "Go ahead, child, draw what you see." What did you see? How many did you see? What else did you see? ". The child says: "I saw three similar leaves." Then you say: "Then let's draw those three leaves." See, we study mathematics, but we also study art, as well as practice remembering what we perceive. We first provided an environment for children to perceive by making them walk, developing and discharging them psychomotorically, and then turning these into academic skills. Observing, drawing, telling the color and number, responding to instructions regarding time and place, painting the correct color, etc. It is one of the academic skills that can be acquired at a young age. If the child acquires such academic skills at an early age, he will begin to demonstrate the skills he has acquired in the future, when the courses in primary education are loaded and the tasks that require more concentration increase. For example, let's say we bought a book, there are birds, flowers and so on in the

book. There are pictures, and there are spaces next to the pictures. The teacher is expected to ask the child a question: "When did you see this flower? Write down its history" or "Where did you see it, what is its name?". Such a study actually gives the following message to teachers and parents: "Take the child around, put him/her in different learning environments, but do not take the child around haphazardly, take him/her with a purpose." At the end of such an activity, the teacher said, "Do you know in which other countries something similar to what we saw would happen?" can develop the topic by saying, arouse curiosity and direct the child to research, go to the library, or browse the internet. Such a study actually gives the following message to teachers and parents: "Take the child around, put him/her in different learning environments, but do not take the child around haphazardly, take him/her with a purpose." At the end of such an activity, the teacher said, "Do you know in which other countries something similar to what we saw would happen?" can develop the topic by saying, arouse curiosity and direct the child to research, go to the library, or browse the internet.

A certain method should be determined to help children use technology devices such as computers or televisions, which are among the most important products of the modern world. Technological tools undoubtedly have a very important place in education, but they must be used for the "right purposes". Sometimes good documentaries, children's programs and cartoons are broadcast on television, but parents should examine such programs and decide together with the child on a few suitable programs for him, instead of allowing him to stay in front of the screen all the time. They should sit with the child and watch one or two programs a week and then turn off the television. Parents should sometimes, if not always, encourage the child to watch carefully and then draw conclusions from the program or movie together, that is, ask the child to deduce the main idea of the program he watched. Or we can ask him questions that develop his imagination, such as "If you made this movie, what would it be called?" Also, the TV button should not be pressed as soon as you come home. So, what happens when we press? We are giving the message to the child, "Son, this is such an important tool that we cannot live without it." Similar things can be said about computer use. Technological tools should be turned on and used when necessary and then turned off. Otherwise, many things to do in life will not be done and family members will spend unnecessarily idle time at home and disconnected from each other. This shakes the concept of "family-centered family" and a communication gap begins between family members. However, as parents and teachers, we need to constantly question what message we are giving to our children with our attitudes and behaviors, that is, to be the right model.

Living a "family"-centered life is also an essential issue in child development. Yes, we should live "family"-centered, not "child"-centered or "mother"-centered or "father"-centered, so that family members can perceive the home as a warm place, express themselves easily, and meet their needs. It is very important to do many things to do at home by sharing them as a family.

Because we have enough money, we buy an LCD television in the living room to watch sports and TV series, and a television in the kitchen so our mothers can watch while preparing meals; If we put a television in the child's room, then we cannot know who is watching what and why. The same is true for the computer, that is, which sites your child visits and browses on the internet, who he or she "chats" with, what he or she engages in; you can't control it. Of course, children may want these. Children can always want something because they are still in the "egocentric" period, they can always want something for themselves, but should you get it? He is still looking at the issues from his own perspective, but you must gradually teach him the ability to look at things from the other side, that is, to establish "empathy". It is also necessary not to confuse enthusiasm with the concepts of a real need and desire. You should say, "Of course, my dear, you can want this, that too, you can also want the second shoe, but there is no need for this because our family has different needs, we should allocate money for them and use some of our budget for this." You should even make a budget together and decide on consumption items together. Very few families in Azerbaijan can do this, and they are happy when they do it. We recommend this to everyone: Decide together as a family. "If something is to be bought for the house or for the kitchen, what does it have to do with it? Will the child decide? Are we going to take them on top of us? Because there is another message you will give by behaving like this, pedagogically: "You are important, you are a member of our family; We value and respect you; "Your decisions may give us an idea that we would never have thought of." Does he want a wardrobe in his room? Get up and go buy him a wardrobe together. Measure his room together, let him decide which wall he wants to lean against and other details. Here, that cupboard is an excuse, there are other messages we want to give by suggesting this: First of all, we will learn to be a family, maybe we will have a meal while we are out, and we will do it together with excitement and enthusiasm. Because marriages need motivation from time to time. Husband, wife, children, grandmother, grandfather, whoever is at home, get up and go, walk around together, feel the excitement together, and let your child hear it along with you: "How much is that? What are the features of which material and which one is more suitable? Which one can my family buy? What kind of family is our family? Do I have to be frugal too?" Let him think about such matters. Once you have a closet, you need to teach it how to take care of it and place it together. Only with such an approach - without being prepared - can the child be equipped with life skills and feel in an accepting and tolerant family. Besides, how will you teach the skill of being a "right citizen" without teaching frugality? Computer, television etc. He can't teach him the social values and family rules he needs to learn. In other words, living in a community is not enough for a child to learn everything on its own. It is necessary for the adults around them to interpret the characteristics of the culture they live in and convey them to the child. It is very important for the child to learn through the parent. When you get home, share with your child what you

experienced that day. This also leads to warm communication and a healthy bond between you. He will tell us about his experiences today, and we will listen and chat with him so that he can experience the beauty of being listened to and feel confident in himself. In addition, he should gain listening skills and progress towards healthy communication with the people around him. They have to learn about life: Where is what? Who is who? What's this? What do people say about them? Because, amid the hustle and bustle of daily life, children are made to sit in a corner without sharing their home life. Just because the children are preparing for the exam, they are not allowed to clean, the housework is not shared with them, they are given mobile phones, money is given, and service is arranged. Then the children spend about six years between private teaching institutions, schools, homes and cafes. As humans, we all need to be outdoors as much as possible, from infancy to old age, because that's how we were created. We are part of nature. As we move away from nature and spontaneity, material and spiritual problems arise. There is a very valuable saying on this subject, but I can't remember who said it, it says: "I have never seen a new technology that did not necessarily cause something wrong, that did not have a negative side effect." It's a pessimistic sentence, but it also has a grain of truth. Something is invented, that invention either causes cancer or its waste cannot be easily eliminated, etc. As you know, technology is already developing very rapidly, products are becoming smaller and smaller, and technological waste is a problem. Technology is good, but it also has its negative effects. A child-centered problem-solving approach; It requires supportive parent and teacher attitudes and behaviors that use open-ended materials that lead to research, investigation, and collaborative problem solving." I would also like to remind that the accuracy of the child-centered education and training approach has been demonstrated by research conducted in all countries, and that these sentences coincide with what I have emphasized so far.

There is also a nice evaluation of Froebel in this book (Froebel is a German scientist known as the founder of pre-school education institutions and kindergartens), he made an analogy between educators and gardeners (The analogy method is a method that facilitates learning by building a bridge between the unknown and the known). . It says: "The educator is the gardener, and the kindergarten is the children's garden." In this garden, Froebel emphasizes that children should be educated in a way that ensures harmony between their natural structure and the structure of the universe. Gardeners should provide such education in this children's garden so that the child can establish a relationship between his own nature and the structure of the universe and receive education in a way that he can cope with the universe. What a beautiful analogy this is. Many theorists state that we are a part of the natural environment, so technology cannot replace nature and, on the contrary, will blunt the development of our ties with nature. Should parents primarily concern themselves with their children's affective skills?

This subject includes moral development, that is, moral behavior. "For a behavior to be moral, it must

pass through three stages in a healthy way," say experts. The first is to interpret the situation, the second is to decide, and the third is to proceed on the path to follow. This three-stage independent progression is closely related to both cognitive development and affective development. Let's say a person encounters a situation and interprets it. In order to make decisions and proceed on the path he will follow, he needs two different skills, one is cognitive and the other is affective. You can draw the following conclusion from here: As teachers and primary educators at home, parents should please focus on their children's affective skills first, cognitive skills come after. However, what we mean by moral development here is the progress we have made in terms of the skills required to acquire the social norms and values of the society we live in. Adults who will be involved in raising children in early childhood should not forget that "Young children learn important things not by being told, but by self-constructing information while playing with other children and interacting with the physical environment." You know, if you remind him many times, "Put on your cardigan, baby, you'll get cold," he makes fun of it again and forgets about it. However, while playing or talking to other children, he looks at his friends, they also have it, he feels cold and then he says: "I'm cold, mom, give me my cardigan." In this way, he becomes aware of himself. In addition, play provides such opportunities that the child's body and mind come together. Vygotsky, a theorist who emphasizes the effect of the environment on children's cognitive development, states that this interaction is embedded in the social structure and is significantly affected by it. He suggests establishing a social structure to realize this interaction, involving children in social systems, community projects, such as volunteer work, and then monitoring and evaluating them. Now, no one pays attention to children's manual skills or equips them with life skills; Everyone protects their children, takes care of them, feeds them, and feeds them incorrectly - but unfortunately they do not allow play. In short, we do whatever it takes to get a wrongly raised child. He is unhealthy, robust, safe in the apartment floors, has everything, but he is a lonely child. Apparently they have no shortcomings, but in fact such children have so many shortcomings.

Another issue that especially teacher parents complain about is this: They consume all their energy while taking care of students all day long at school, and when they come home, they state that they cannot pay enough attention to their own children and sometimes even hurt them. Of course, this situation is similarly valid for other working parents.

This situation includes "learned helplessness" and "negative self-attribution" as expressed in psychology. In fact, you can educate yourself on this subject, get consultancy, as long as you ask. Of course, this can be supported in different ways; Individuals' personal development can be supported through movies and theater plays of married adults, seminars can be given, and people can be told, "No matter what happens around you, you are important because you are parents, take care of yourself, take care of yourself." Unfortunately, when people get married and have children, they leave

aside their previous pursuits - hobbies (in fact, unfortunately, it is known that the majority did not have such pursuits before!), they do not seek to improve themselves, they do not read books, they do not follow the developments and social events in the world and in their country. The vast majority are in a vicious cycle of going from home to work and from work to home. They complain, but when we say "come on" they just remain spectators and are not willing to participate. One of the main reasons for this is that they have accepted being just spectators by watching broadcasts on TV and the internet since a young age and are becoming increasingly idle. People who are very tense at home forget that the tension stems mainly from the work they do and their relationships with each other. Waking up early in the morning with joy, getting ready right away, preparing breakfast together, bidding farewell to children or spouses when they leave the house, and waving after them. There is a mutual message in all of these: "We love each other, we are all important. In order to make those around you happy, you must first find ways to make yourself happy. People need positive feedback. Share everything you can with your children and spouse, tell about your day, but do not start the sentence negatively while doing this. Nowadays, people are under tension because they cannot express themselves.

Young children's emotions, interests and values are variable; It cannot be preserved from one situation to another, its decisions can change quickly. If parents

know these, they will not beat themselves and their children. I would like to point out that children should be raised freely by parents, but there is no harm in telling them that not everything they want can come true, so that they can understand their limits. Sometimes it seems that the adults in the family are tense as a result of their busy workload and neglecting themselves for the sake of their children. Adults need to improve themselves by knowing what is right and starting from this point. In order to do this, it is necessary to want to change, develop and be determined. In the modern age, the world of children is changing and parents must manage to develop and take responsibility under these conditions.

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